

Do we already possess the vaccine to SARS-CoV-2?

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SARS-CoV-2 has been rapidly spreading throughout the world for more than four months already. Yet, several key parameters required for accurately modeling its spread remain elusive. For example, the basic reproduction number, R_0 , which indicates the number of viral transmissions from each infected person at the beginning of the viral spread in the population, remains controversial and inconclusive. Its value, estimated over the last few months, has ranged from 2.2 to 11, with higher values estimated for highly interacting and often confined populations, such as those found in cruise ships¹⁻⁵. This value is important for determining the speed of the spread and the maximal portion of infections in a population ($1-1/R_0$).

Since the virus causes a newly emerging disease, it is commonly assumed that no immunity to this virus has been developed. Indeed, serologic tests showed a lack of cross-reactivity of the viral spike (S) and nucleocapsid (N) proteins from sera obtained from donors exposed to other coronaviruses⁶.

Nevertheless, we believe that this viewpoint should be challenged in light of several complete or random surveys to detect the prevalence of the virus in different populations. Analysis of these surveys revealed that significant antiviral immunity may already be present in certain populations, which may even reach up to 60%-80%.

Whereas the infection upper limit for a naïve population is predicted to be in the range of 55% to 82% in general populations (R_0 value between 2.2 and 5.7) and 91% in confined environments such as cruise ships (R_0 value ~ 11), to the best of our knowledge, all reports and representative surveys indicate an infection upper limit of up to approximately 15% in general populations and of up to approximately 50% in confined environments (Table 1).

Such upper limits may occur due to several reasons and factors. The first possibility is that the majority of the population was not sufficiently exposed to the virus. However, this possibility seems less likely in the cases involving the three cruise ships, where shared facilities were used frequently and there were high interactions between the passengers and the crew members.

Another possibility is that the surveys were taken at a time that the infection was still exponentially growing, or that containment or prevention of the viral spread in these sampled populations was successful at these levels. However, the probability of sampling a population or stopping or containing the viral spread at a given narrow range during the relatively short exponential expansion period is low (doubling time every 1.5 to 5 days, depending on the

environment). The saturation phase, in which the disease peaks, is longer; therefore, it has a higher probability to be sampled.

We therefore suggest that a significant percentage of different populations may have pre-existing, non-humoral immunity to the SARS-CoV-2 virus, which provides an upper limit for the spread of the virus. The observed difference in the immunity levels may derive from various factors including age and genetics, as well as exposure to the immunity-conferring agent, as elaborated below.

How can there be pre-existing non-humoral immunity to a newly identified virus? We suggest that cellular immunity to the SARS-CoV-2 is conferred from previous infections by closely related viruses. SARS-CoV-2 has six “relatives”, which have been infecting much of the world population for many years: SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, human coronavirus (HCoV) -229E, -OC43, -NL63, and -HKU1.

The SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV, which cause a severe respiratory syndrome, are rare in the general population. However, the latter four HCoVs, which are common throughout the world, are the second most frequent cause of common colds and account for an average percentage of 15% of the acute respiratory infections in the general population of the United States, for example⁷. Similar to influenza infections, their yearly infection percentages are variable, ranging from 1% to 35% of the population annually⁷. The infection spread of these HCoV species may vary greatly in different countries, parts of the world, and in different years. Importantly, these viruses display a relatively high genome similarity of ~50% to the novel SARS-CoV-2 virus⁸.

Since different epitopes from the S and N viral proteins display limited cross-reactivity in eliciting an antibody response between the different HCoVs and SARS-CoV2⁶, we hypothesized that cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTLs) may contribute to the pre-existing immunity. CTLs recognize and eliminate virally infected cells by recognizing peptides, which are displayed on antigen-presenting cells via the human leukocyte antigen (HLA) system. Importantly, protective CTLs were previously shown for SARS-CoV⁹; their protective immunity in the form of memory CTLs can last for periods of over a year^{9,10}. Therefore, we speculated that cross-protection may emerge from CTLs recognizing viral peptides that are common to SARS-CoV2 and that are found among the other HCoV members, a possibility that could explain the observed upper limit of the infected populations.

To this end, we sought to identify the peptide repertoire that is shared between SARS-CoV-2 and the four HCoVs that cause mild symptoms. We found a total of 886 SARS-CoV-2 potential epitopes that are also present within at least one other HCoV (Figure 1A and Supplementary Table 1). Interestingly, the highest number of shared peptides (630) was found between SARS-CoV-2 and HCoV-OC43, which is known to account for most of the HCoV infections worldwide¹¹.

Next, we predicted the binding affinity of the 886 potentially cross-protective peptides to 81 different HLA-A, -B complexes using the NetMHC 4.0 Server¹², in order to evaluate their potential to be generated via the major histocompatibility class (MHC) I antigen processing pathway. Out of a total of 219 predicted binders (predicted affinity < 500nM), 80 peptides are

expected to display a strong binding affinity on at least one HLA allele ($< 50\text{nM}$, see Figure 1B and Supplementary Table 1). Conversely, we noted that 667 potentially cross-protective peptides exhibited no appreciable binding affinity ($< 500\text{nM}$) to any of the tested HLAs.

Previous studies correlated genetic variability among HLA alleles with viral susceptibility including SARS-CoV¹³ and SARS-CoV-2¹⁴. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that different populations, which differ in their HLA genetics, may display a distinct pre-existing immunity to the virus. As shown in Figure 1C and Supplementary Table 1, HLA-A is predicted to display a greater ability to present the conserved HCoV-SARS-CoV-2 repertoire of epitopes than is HLA-B. Based on this notion, pre-immunity toward SARS-CoV-2 is affected by several factors, namely, the distribution of different HLAs in populations, and the prevalence of different HCoVs in populations prior to the spread of SARS-CoV-2.

In support of this notion, it was recently suggested that immunity to SARS-CoV-2 due to mild (30%) antibody mediated cross-immunity from HCoVs will effectively limit or impede the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 for up to three years. Furthermore, the authors suggested that if SARS-CoV-2-induced cross-immunity against HCoVs will reach up to 70%, the incidence of all HCoVs could disappear¹⁵. However, we suggest that since HCoVs are widely spread, it would be more reasonable to assume that our predicated cellular cross-immunity between HCoVs and SARS-CoV-2 would result in limiting or slowing the spread of the latter, not vice versa.

An additional factor that may affect immunity is the transmission of mild HCoVs between individuals in a population, and particularly by children. It was shown that seropositivity to HCoV-229E and -OC43 rises during the first five years of life^{7,16,17}. This is most likely because children manifest mutual encounters involving more physical contact, compared with adults. In line with this view, a recent study concluded that children under the age of 10 are significantly less susceptible to infection by SARS-CoV-2, compared with other age groups¹⁸. This result suggests that children may be pre-immune more than adults are. Since children are a large source of HCoV infections, and consequent transfer of immunity within their families, populations with a large number of children are expected to be more immune to the new SARS-CoV-2 virus than are populations with fewer children.

If indeed, natural immunity pre-exists, then the reproduction number value, i.e., the value measuring the spread of the virus in naïve populations, is probably much higher than initially thought, based on the initial premise that all populations are immunologically naïve. Adding this parameter to the predictive epidemiological tools (and adding a pre-immune population parameter) may fundamentally change the predictions of the course of the pandemic.

If our hypothesis is correct, then the observed percentage of the non-infected group comprises both pre-immune people and those not infected due to herd immunity. For example, the observed percentage of infected passengers on the Diamond Princess cruise ship is 19%. If we use the estimated $R_0=11$ value⁵, then without pre-immunity, the maximal infection rate would be 91% ($1-1/R_0$). However, assuming that 79% of the population possesses pre-immunity, this would bring the maximal level to the observed 19% (the maximal level is calculated by multiplying the standard $1-1/R_0$ expression by the proportion of those not pre-immune, which is 21% in this

case). Thus, these calculations can determine the percentage of the population that was pre-immune to the virus.

Another implication of the existence of an immunity hypothesis is that the calculated severe cases and the mortality rates are significantly lower than estimated, because a significant portion of the population is already immune to it.

The most important implication that will result from establishing the above hypothesis is that deliberately exposing populations to milder forms or variants of HCoVs¹⁹ may prove to be an efficient vaccination strategy against SARS-CoV-2. In this regard, the current strategy of closing schools and kindergartens may prove to be an unfortunate mistake, since it dramatically impedes the transmission of the milder HCoVs. Vaccinating everyone in the population using these HCoVs will result in an immunity that could eventually lead to diminishing and eliminating this devastating SARS-CoV-2 pandemic virus and to restoring normalcy, safety, and stability to the world.

Table 1. Surveys for carriage of SARS-CoV-2

Survey type	Surveyed population	Total population	Total tested	COVID-19 Positive	Percentage positive	Reference
Confined ships	Diamond Princess	3711	3711	712	19	link
	Theodore Roosevelt	4870	4574	669	15	link
	Charles de Gaulle	2300	2010	1081	54	link
General population	Gangelt, Germany	12529	500	N/A	15	link
	Maternity wards, New York City, USA	215	214	33	15	²⁰
	Robbio, Italy	6000	1300	N/A	12	link

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Figure 1. **A.** Linear epitopes of 8-11 aa match between the four HCoVs and SARS-CoV-2. **B.** Linear epitopes match as in A and their HLA putatively binding counterparts, with blue and red indicating the number of tightly (<50nM) and loosely (<500nM and >50nM) binding peptides, respectively. **C.** Distribution of HLA allelic presentation of the first highly 70 binders from matching peptide as in A, with blue and red indicating the number of tightly (<50nM) and loosely (<500nM and >50nM) binding peptides, respectively.